

Counterparty Credit Risk Framework

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a framework for capturing counterparty credit risk by accounting default correlation. We find that the CDS premium and the default correlations/comrelation have a negative relation. Intuitively, a protection seller who is positively correlated with the reference entity, i.e., a wrong way risk, should charge a lower premium for selling credit protection. Next, we also find that the impacts of the default correlations and comrelation are approximately linear. Finally, our study shows that the sensitivity slopes of the CDS premium to the default correlations and comrelation are negative. Slope measures the rate of change in the premium as a result of a change in the default dependence.

Key Words: asset pricing; credit risk modeling; collateralization; comvariance; comrelation; correlation, CDS.

1 Introduction

Central to the reduced-form models is the assumption that multiple defaults are independent conditional on the state of the economy. In reality, however, the default of one party might affect the default probabilities of other parties. Collin-Dufresne et al. (2003) and Zhang and Jorion (2007) find that a major credit event at one firm is associated with significant increases in the credit spreads of other firms. Giesecke (2004), Das et al. (2006), and Lando and Nielsen (2010) find that a defaulting firm can weaken the firms in its network of business links. These findings have important implications for the management of credit risk portfolios, where default relationships need to be explicitly modeled.

The endogenous approaches include the contagion (or infectious) models and frailty models. The frailty models (see Duffie et al. (2009), Koopman et al. (2011), etc) describe default clustering based on some unobservable explanatory variables. In variations of contagion or infectious type models (see Davis and Lo (2001), Jarrow and Yu (2001), etc.), the assumption of conditional independence is relaxed and default intensities are made to depend on default events of other entities. Contagion and frailty models fill an important gap but at the cost of analytic tractability. They can be especially difficult to implement for large portfolios.

Given a default model, one can value a risky derivative contract and compute credit value adjustment (CVA) that is a relatively new area of financial derivative modeling and trading. CVA is the expected loss arising from the default of a counterparty (see Brigo and Capponi (2008), Lipton and Sepp (2009), Pykhtin and Zhu (2006), Gregory (2009), Bielecki et al (2013) and Crepey (2015), etc.)

This paper presents a new framework for valuing defaultable financial contracts with or without collateral arrangements. The framework characterizes default dependencies exogenously, and models collateral processes directly based on the fundamental principals of collateral agreements. For brevity we focus on CDS contracts, but many of the points we make are equally applicable to other derivatives. CDS has trilateral credit risk, where three parties – buyer, seller and reference entity – are defaultable.

The standard CDS pricing model in the market assumes that there is no counterparty risk. Although this oversimplified model may be accepted in normal market conditions, its reliability in times of distress

has recently been questioned. In fact, counterparty risk has become one of the most dangerous threats to the CDS market. For some time now it has been realized that, in order to value a CDS properly, counterparty effects have to be taken into account (see ECB (2009)).

We bring the concept of *comvariance* into the area of credit risk modeling to capture the statistical relationship among three or more random variables. Comvariance was first introduced to economics by Deardorff (1982), who used this measurement to correlate three factors in international trading. Furthermore, we define a new statistics, *comrelation*, as a scaled version of comvariance. Accounting for default correlations and comrelations becomes important in determining CDS premia, especially during the credit crisis.

There is a significant increase in the use of collateral for CDS after the recent financial crises. Many people believe that, if a CDS is fully collateralized, there is no risk of failure to pay. Collateral posting regimes are originally designed and utilized for bilateral risk products, e.g., interest rate swap (IRS), but there are many reasons to be concerned about the success of collateral posting in offsetting the risk of CDS contracts. First, the value of CDS contracts tends to move very suddenly with big jumps, whereas the price movements of *IRS* contracts are far smoother and less volatile than *CDS* prices. Second, CDS spreads can widen very rapidly. Third, CDS contracts have many more risk factors than *IRS* contracts. In fact, our model shows that full collateralization *cannot* eliminate counterparty risk completely for a CDS contract.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Pricing multilateral defaultable financial contract is elaborated on in Section 2; numerical results are provided in Section 3; the conclusions are presented in Section 4. All proofs and some detailed derivations are contained in the appendices.

2 Pricing Financial Contracts Subject to Multilateral Credit Risk

In the reduced-form approach, the stopping (or default) time τ_i of firm i is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined by,

$$\tau_i = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h_i(s, Z_s) ds \geq H_i \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $h_i(t)$ or $h_i(t, Z_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Z_t , and H_i is a unit exponential random variable independent of Z_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p_i(t, s) := P_i(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z_t) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h_i(u) du\right) \quad (2a)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is given by

$$q_i(t, s) := P_i(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z_t) = 1 - p_i(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h_i(u) du\right) \quad (2b)$$

The interest in the financial industry for the modeling and pricing of multilateral defaultable instruments arises mainly in two respects: in the management of credit risk at a portfolio level and in the valuation of credit derivatives. Central to the valuation and risk management of credit derivatives and risky portfolios is the problem of default relationship.

A CDS is normally used to transfer the credit risk of a reference entity between two counterparties. The contract reduces the credit risk of the reference entity but gives rise to another form of risk: *counterparty risk*. Since the dealers are highly concentrated within a small group, any of them may be too big to fail. The interconnected nature, with dealers being tied to each other through chains of OTC derivatives, results in increased contagion risk. Due to its concentration and interconnectedness, the CDS market seems to pose a systemic risk to financial market stability. In fact, the CDS is blamed for playing a pivotal role in the collapse of Lehman Brothers and the disintegration of AIG.

Let A denote the protection buyer, B denote the protection seller and C denote the reference entity. The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. Therefore, the default indicator Y_j for firm j ($j = A$ or B or C) follows a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability q_j , and value 0 with survival probability p_j . The marginal default distributions can be determined by the reduced-form models. The joint distributions of a multivariate Bernoulli variable can be

easily obtained via the marginal distributions by introducing extra correlations. The joint probability representations of a trivariate Bernoulli distribution (see Teugels (1990)) are given by

$$p_{000} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 0) = p_A p_B p_C + p_C \sigma_{AB} + p_B \sigma_{AC} + p_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (3a)$$

$$p_{100} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 0) = q_A p_B p_C - p_C \sigma_{AB} - p_B \sigma_{AC} + q_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (3b)$$

$$p_{010} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 0) = p_A q_B p_C - p_C \sigma_{AB} + q_B \sigma_{AC} - p_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (3c)$$

$$p_{001} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 1) = p_A p_B q_C + q_C \sigma_{AB} - p_B \sigma_{AC} - p_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (3d)$$

$$p_{110} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 0) = q_A q_B p_C + p_C \sigma_{AB} - q_B \sigma_{AC} - q_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (3e)$$

$$p_{101} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 1) = q_A p_B q_C - q_C \sigma_{AB} + p_B \sigma_{AC} - q_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (3f)$$

$$p_{011} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 1) = p_A q_B q_C - q_C \sigma_{AB} - q_B \sigma_{AC} + p_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (3g)$$

$$p_{111} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 1) = q_A q_B q_C + q_C \sigma_{AB} + q_B \sigma_{AC} + q_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (3h)$$

where

$$\theta_{ABC} := E((Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)(Y_C - q_C)) \quad (3i)$$

We introduce the concept of *comvariance* into credit risk modeling arena to exploit any statistical relationship among multiple random variables. Furthermore, we define a new statistic, *comrelation*, as a scaled version of comvariance (just like correlation is a scaled version of covariance) as follows:

Definition 1: For three random variables X_A , X_B , and X_C , let μ_A , μ_B , and μ_C denote the means of X_A , X_B , and X_C . The comrelation of X_A , X_B , and X_C is defined by

$$\zeta_{ABC} = \frac{E[(X_A - \mu_A)(X_B - \mu_B)(X_C - \mu_C)]}{\sqrt[3]{E|X_A - \mu_A|^3 \times E|X_B - \mu_B|^3 \times E|X_C - \mu_C|^3}} \quad (4)$$

According to the Holder inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |E((X_A - \mu_A)(X_B - \mu_B)(X_C - \mu_C))| &\leq E|(X_A - \mu_A)(X_B - \mu_B)(X_C - \mu_C)| \\ &\leq \sqrt[3]{E|X_A - \mu_A|^3 \times E|X_B - \mu_B|^3 \times E|X_C - \mu_C|^3} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Obviously, the comrelation is in the range of $[-1, 1]$. Given the comrelation, Equation (3i) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_{ABC} &:= E((Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)(Y_C - q_C)) = \zeta_{ABC} \sqrt[3]{E|Y_A - q_A|^3 \times E|Y_B - q_B|^3 \times E|Y_C - q_C|^3} \\ &= \zeta_{ABC} \sqrt[3]{p_A q_A (p_A^2 + q_A^2) p_B q_B (p_B^2 + q_B^2) p_C q_C (p_C^2 + q_C^2)}\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$ and $E|Y_j - q_j|^3 = p_j q_j (p_j^2 + q_j^2)$, $j=A, B, \text{ or } C$.

If we have a series of n measurements of X_A , X_B , and X_C written as x_{Ai} , x_{Bi} and x_{Ci} where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, the sample *comrelation coefficient* can be obtained as:

$$\zeta_{ABC} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{Ai} - \mu_A)(x_{Bi} - \mu_B)(x_{Ci} - \mu_C)}{\sqrt[3]{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_{Ai} - \mu_A|^3 \times \sum_{i=1}^n |x_{Bi} - \mu_B|^3 \times \sum_{i=1}^n |x_{Ci} - \mu_C|^3}}\quad (7)$$

More generally, we define the *comrelation* in the context of n random variables as

Definition 2: For n random variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , let μ_i denote the mean of X_i where $i=1, \dots, n$. The *comrelation* of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n is defined as

$$\zeta_{12\dots n} = \frac{E[(X_1 - \mu_1)(X_2 - \mu_2) \cdots (X_n - \mu_n)]}{\sqrt[n]{E|X_1 - \mu_1|^n \times E|X_2 - \mu_2|^n \cdots E|X_n - \mu_n|^n}}\quad (8)$$

Correlation is just a specific case of *comrelation* where $n = 2$. Again, the *comrelation* $\zeta_{12\dots n}$ is in the range of $[-1, 1]$ according to the Holder inequality.

2.1 Risky valuation without collateralization

Let valuation date be t . Suppose that a CDS has m scheduled payments represented as $X_i = -sN\delta(T_{i-1}, T_i)$ with payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m where $i=1, \dots, m$, $\delta(T_{i-1}, T_i)$ denotes the accrual factor for period (T_{i-1}, T_i) , N denotes the notional/principal, and s denotes the CDS premium. Party A pays the premium/fee to party B if reference entity C does not default. In return, party B agrees to pay the protection amount to party A if reference entity C defaults before the maturity. We have the following proposition.

Proposition 1: The value of the CDS is given by

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-2} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) \Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i) R(T_{i-1}, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t\right]\quad (9a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$O(T_j, T_{j+1}) = \mathbf{1}_{(V(T_{j+1}) + X_{j+1}) \geq 0} \phi_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \mathbf{1}_{(V(T_{j+1}) + X_{j+1}) < 0} \phi_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) \quad (9b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) = & \left\{ p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \varphi_A(T_{j+1}) \right. \\ & + p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \sigma_{AB}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_A(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \\ & + \sigma_{AC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_A(T_{j+1})) + q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (\bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \right] \\ & + \sigma_{BC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1})) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) (\varphi_A(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \right] \\ & \left. + \theta_{ABC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (-1 + \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_A(T_{j+1})) \right\} D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (9c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) = & \left\{ p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) \right. \\ & + p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \sigma_{AB}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \\ & + \sigma_{AC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1})) + q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (\varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \right] \\ & + \sigma_{BC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1})) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) (\bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \right] \\ & \left. + \theta_{ABC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (-1 + \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_B(T_{j+1})) \right\} D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (9d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(T_j, T_{j+1}) = & \left\{ p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) \right. \\ & + p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) q_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \\ & + q_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) \sigma_{AB}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \\ & - \sigma_{AC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[p_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1})) + q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (\varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \right] \\ & - \sigma_{BC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[p_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1})) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) (\bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \right] \\ & \left. + \theta_{ABC}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_B(T_{j+1})) \right\} D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (9e)$$

where $R(T_j, T_{j+1}) = (N(1 - \varphi_C(T_{j+1})) - \alpha(T_j, T_{j+1}))$, $\alpha(T_j, T_{j+1}) = sN\delta(T_S, T)/2$, and $X_i = -sN\delta(T_j, T_{j+1})$.

Proof: See the Appendix.

We may think of $O(t, T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor for the premium and $\Omega(t, T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor for the default payment. Proposition 1 says that the pricing process of a multiple-payment instrument has a backward nature since there is no way of knowing which risk-adjusted discounting rate should be used without knowledge of the future value. Only on the maturity date, the value of an instrument and the decision strategy are clear. Therefore, the evaluation must be done in a backward fashion, working from the final payment date towards the present. This type of valuation process is referred to as backward induction.

Proposition 1 provides a general form for pricing a CDS. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that counterparties *A* and *B* are default-free, i.e., $p_j = 1$, $q_j = 0$, $\rho_{kl} = 0$, and $\varsigma_{ABC} = 0$, where $j=A$ or B and $k, l=A, B, \text{ or } C$, we derive the following corollary.

Corollary 1: *If counterparties A and B are default-free, the value of the CDS is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-2} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)\Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i)R(T_{i-1}, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[D(t, T_i)p_C(t, T_i)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[D(t, T_i)p_C(t, T_{i-1})q_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)R(T_{i-1}, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $O(T_{i-1}, T_i) = D(T_{i-1}, T_i)p_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)$; $\Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i) = D(T_{i-1}, T_i)q_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)$.

The proof of this corollary becomes straightforward according to Proposition 1 by setting $\rho_{kl} = 0$, $\varphi_{AB} = 0$, $\varsigma_{ABC} = 0$, $p_j = 1$, $q_j = 0$, $p_C(t, T_i) = \prod_{g=0}^{i-1} p(T_g, T_{g+1})$, and $D(t, T_i) = \prod_{g=0}^{i-1} D(T_g, T_{g+1})$.

If we further assume that the discount factor and the default probability of the reference entity are uncorrelated and the recovery rate φ_C is constant, we have

Corollary 2: *Assume that i) counterparties A and B are default-free, ii) the discount factor and the default probability of the reference entity are uncorrelated; iii) the recovery rate φ_C is constant; the value of the CDS is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m P(t, T_i)\bar{p}_C(t, T_{i-1})\bar{q}_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)(N(1 - \varphi_C) - \alpha(T_{i-1}, T_i)) - \sum_{i=1}^m P(t, T_i)\bar{p}_C(t, T_i)sN\delta(T_{i-1}, T_i) \quad (11)$$

where $P(t, T_i) = E[D(t, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t]$ denotes the bond price, $\bar{p}_C(t, T_i) = E[p_C(t, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t]$, $\bar{q}_C(t, T_i) = 1 - \bar{p}_C(t, T_i)$, $\bar{p}(t, T_{i-1})\bar{q}(T_{i-1}, T_i) = \bar{p}(t, T_{i-1}) - \bar{p}(t, T_i)$.

This corollary is easily proved according to Corollary 1 by setting $E[XY | \mathcal{F}_t] = E[X | \mathcal{F}_t]E[Y | \mathcal{F}_t]$ when X and Y are uncorrelated. *Corollary 2 is the formula for pricing CDS in the market.*

Our methodology can be extended to the cases where the number of parties $n \geq 4$. A generating function for the (probability) joint distribution (see details in Teugels (1990)) of n -variate Bernoulli can be expressed as

$$p^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} p_n & -1 \\ q_n & 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} p_{n-1} & -1 \\ q_{n-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \dots \otimes \begin{bmatrix} p_1 & -1 \\ q_1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \sigma^{(n)} \quad (12)$$

where \otimes denotes the Kronecker product; $p^{(n)} = \{p_k^{(n)}\}$ and $\sigma^{(n)} = \{\sigma_k^{(n)}\}$ are vectors containing 2^n components: $p_k^{(n)} = p_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n}$, $k = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^n k_i 2^{i-1}$, $k_i \in \{0, 1\}$; $\sigma_k^{(n)} = \sigma_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = E\left(\prod_{i=1}^n (Y_i - q_i)^{k_i}\right)$.

2.2 Risky valuation with collateralization

In a typical collateral procedure, a financial instrument is periodically marked-to-market and the collateral is adjusted to reflect changes in value. The collateral is called as soon as the mark-to-market (MTM) value rises above the given collateral threshold, or more precisely, above the threshold amount plus the minimum transfer amount. Thus, the collateral amount posted at time t is given by

$$C(t) = \begin{cases} V(t) - H(t) & \text{if } V(t) > H(t) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where $H(t)$ is the collateral threshold. In particular, $H(t) = 0$ corresponds to full-collateralization¹; $H > 0$ represents partial/under-collateralization; and $H < 0$ is associated with over-collateralization. Full collateralization becomes increasingly popular at the transaction level. In this paper, we focus on full collateralization only, i.e., $C(t) = V(t)$.

According to the ISDA (2013), almost all CDSs are fully collateralized. Many people believe that full collateralization can eliminate counterparty risk completely for CDS.

We assume that a CDS is fully collateralized, i.e., the posting of collateral is equal to the amount of the current *MTM* value: $C(t) = V(t)$. For a discrete one-period (t, u) economy, there are several possible states at time u : i) A , B , and C survive with probability p_{000} . The instrument value is equal to the market value $V(u)$; ii) A and B survive, but C defaults with probability p_{001} . The instrument value is the default

¹ There are three types of collateralization: Full-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is equal to the current MTM value. Partial/under-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is less than the current MTM value. Over-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is greater than the current MTM value.

payment $R(u)$; iii) For the remaining cases, either or both counterparties A and B default. The instrument value is the future value of the collateral $V(t)/D(t,u)$ (Here we consider the time value of money only). The value of the collateralized instrument at time t is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{D(t,u)\left[p_{000}(t,u)V(u) + p_{001}(t,u)R(u)\right.\right. \\ &\quad \left.\left.+ (p_{100}(t,u) + p_{010}(t,u) + p_{110}(t,u) + p_{101}(t,u) + p_{011}(t,u) + p_{111}(t,u))V(t)/D(t,u)\right]\right\} \quad (14a) \\ &= E\left\{D(t,u)\left(p_{000}(t,u)V(s) + p_{001}(t,u)R(u)\right) + (1 - p_{000}(t,u) - p_{001}(t,u))V(t)\right\} \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} &E\left[\left(p_A(t,u)p_B(t,u) + \sigma_{AB}(t,u)\right)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right]V(t) \\ &= E\left\{D(t,u)\left(p_C(t,u)V(u) + q_C(t,u)R(u)\right)\left(p_A(t,u)p_B(t,u) + \sigma_{AB}(t,u)\right)\right. \\ &\quad \left.+ D(t,u)\left(V(u) - R(u)\right)\left(p_B(t,u)\sigma_{AC}(t,u) + p_A(t,u)\sigma_{BC}(t,u) - \theta_{ABC}(t,u)\right)\right\} \quad (14b) \end{aligned}$$

If we assume that $(p_A(t,u)p_B(t,u) + \sigma_{AB}(t,u))$ and $D(t,u)(p_C(t,u)V(u) + q_C(t,u)R(u))$ are uncorrelated, we have

$$V(t) = V^F(t) + \xi_{ABC}(t,u)/\psi_{AB}(t,u) \quad (15a)$$

where

$$V^F(t) = E\left\{D(t,u)\left[p_C(t,u)V(u) + q_C(t,u)R(u)\right]\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (15b)$$

$$\psi_{AB}(t,u) = E\left\{\left[p_A(t,u)p_B(t,u) + \sigma_{AB}(t,u)\right]\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (15c)$$

$$\xi_{ABC}(t,u) = E\left\{D(t,u)\left(p_B(t,u)\sigma_{AC}(t,u) + p_A(t,u)\sigma_{BC}(t,u) - \theta_{ABC}(t,u)\right)\left(V(u) - R(u)\right)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (15d)$$

The first term $V^F(t)$ in equation (15) is the counterparty-risk-free value of the CDS and the second term is the exposure left over under full collateralization, which can be substantial.

Proposition 2: *If a CDS is fully collateralized, the risky value of the CDS is NOT equal to the counterparty-risk-free value, as shown in equation (15).*

Proposition 2 or equation (15) provides a theoretical explanation for the failure of full collateralization in the CDS market. It tells us that under full collateralization the risky value is in general

not equal to the counterparty-risk-free value except in one of the following situations: i) the market value is equal to the default payment, i.e., $V(u) = R(u)$; ii) firms A , B , and C have independent credit risks, i.e., $\rho_{ij} = 0$ and $\varsigma_{ABC} = 0$; or iii) the following relationship holds $p_B \sigma_{AC} + p_A \sigma_{BC} = \theta_{ABC}$.

3 Numerical Results

In our study, we choose a new 5-year CDS with a quarterly payment frequency. Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . Counterparty A buys a protection from counterparty B . All calculations are from the perspective of party A . By definition, a breakeven CDS spread is a premium that makes the market value of a given CDS at inception zero.

Since the payoffs of a CDS are mainly determined by credit events, we need to characterize the evolution of the hazard rates. Here we choose the *Cox-Ingersoll-Ross* (CIR) model. The CIR process has been widely used in the literature of credit risk and is given by

$$dh_t = a(b - h_t)dt + \sigma\sqrt{h_t}dW_t \quad (16)$$

where a denotes the mean reversion speed, b denotes the long-term mean, and σ denotes the volatility.

Table 1: Current/spot market data

This table displays the current (spot) market data used for all calculations in this paper, including the term structure of continuously compounded interest rates, the term structure of A-rated breakeven CDS spreads, and the curve of at-the-money caplet volatilities.

Term (days)	31	91	182	365	548	730	1095	1825	2555	3650	5475
Interest Rate	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.007	0.010	0.016	0.024	0.030	0.035	0.040
	8	7	9	3	1	2		9	6	5	5
Credit Spread	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.005	0.007	0.007	0.009	0.010
	2	2	2	5	9	2	8		9	1	6
Caplet Volatility	0.326	0.331	0.337	0.350	0.364	0.377	0.308	0.247	0.214	0.167	0.163
	7		6	9	1	3		3	1	8	4

Table 2: Risk-neutral parameters for CIR model

This table presents the risk-neutral parameters that are calibrated to the current market shown in Table 1. ‘A+100bps’ represents a ‘100 basis points’ parallel shift in the A-rated CDS spreads.

Credit Quality	A	A+100bps	A+200bps	A+300bps
Long-Term Mean a	0.035	0.056	0.077	0.099
Mean Reverting Speed b	0.14	0.18	0.25	0.36
Volatility σ	0.022	0.028	0.039	0.056

The calibrated parameters are shown in table 2. We assume that interest rates are deterministic and select the regression-based Monte-Carlo simulation (see Longstaff and Schwartz (2001)) to perform risky valuation.

Table 3: Impact of the credit quality of the protection buyer on CDS premia

This table shows how the CDS premium increases as the credit quality of party A decreases. The 1st data column represents the counterparty-risk-free results. For the remaining columns, we assume that party B is risk-free and party A is risky. ‘A+100bps’ represents a ‘100 basis points’ parallel shift in the A-rated CDS spreads. The results in the row ‘Difference from Risk-Free’ = current CDS premium – counterparty-risk-free CDS premium.

Credit Quality	Party A	-	A	A+100bps	A+200bps	A+300bps
	Party B	-	-	-	-	-
CDS premium		0.027	0.02703	0.02708	0.02713	0.02717
Difference from Risk-Free		0	0.003%	0.008%	0.013%	0.017%

Table 4: Impact of the credit quality of the protection seller on CDS premia

This table shows the decrease in the CDS premium with the credit quality of party *B*. The 1st data column represents the counterparty-risk-free results. For the remaining columns, we assume that party *A* is risk-free and party *B* is risky. ‘A+100bps’ represents a ‘100 basis points’ parallel shift in the A-rated CDS spreads. The results in the row ‘Difference from Risk-Free’ = current CDS premium – counterparty-risk-free CDS premium.

Credit Quality	Party A	-	-	-	-	-
	Party B	-	A	A+100bps	A+200bps	A+300bps
CDS premium		0.027	0.02695	0.02687	0.0268	0.02672
Difference from Risk-Free		0.00%	-0.005%	-0.013%	-0.020%	-0.028%

From table 3 and 4, we find that a credit spread of about 100 basis points maps into a CDS premium of about 0.4 basis points for counterparty *A* and about -0.7 basis points for counterparty *B*. The credit impact on the CDS premia is approximately linear. As would be expected, i) the dealer’s credit quality has a larger impact on CDS premia than the investor’s credit quality; ii) the higher the investor’s credit risk, the higher the premium that the dealer charges; iii) the higher the dealer’s credit risk, the lower the premium that the dealer asks. Without considering default correlations and comrelations, we find that, in general, the impact of counterparty risk on CDS premia is relatively small. This is in line with the empirical findings of Arora, Gandhi, and Longstaff (2009).

Figure 1: Impact of default correlations and comrelation on CDS premia

Each curve in this figure illustrates how CDS premium changes as default correlations and comrelation move from -1 to 1. For instance, the curve ‘cor_BC’ represents the sensitivity of the CDS premium to changes in the correlation ρ_{BC} when $\rho_{AB} = \rho_{AC} = \zeta_{ABC} = 0$.

Assume $\varphi_{AB}=0.5$. The impact diagrams of the default correlations and comrelation are shown in Figure 1. From this graph, we can draw the following conclusions: First, the CDS premium and the default correlations/comrelation have a negative relation. Intuitively, a protection seller who is positively correlated with the reference entity (a wrong way risk) should charge a lower premium for selling credit protection. Next, the impacts of the default correlations and comrelation are approximately linear. Finally, the sensitivity slopes of the CDS premium to the default correlations and comrelation are -0.06 to ρ_{AB} ; -0.09 to ρ_{AC} ; -53 to ρ_{BC} ; and -14 to ζ_{ABC} . Slope measures the rate of change in the premium as a result of a change in the default dependence. For instance, a slope of -53 implies that the CDS premium would have to decrease by 53 basis points when a default correlation/comrelation changes from 0 to 1.

4 Conclusion

To capture the default relationships among more than two defaultable entities, we introduce a new statistic: *comrelation*, an analogue to correlation for multiple variables, to exploit any multivariate statistical relationship. Our research shows that accounting for default correlations and comrelations becomes

important, especially under market stress. The existing valuation models in the credit derivatives market, which take into account only pair-wise default correlations, may underestimate credit risk and may be inappropriate.

The model shows that a fully collateralized CDS is not equivalent to a risk-free one. Therefore, we conclude that collateralization designed to mitigate counterparty risk works well for financial instruments subject to bilateral credit risk, but fails for ones subject to multilateral credit risk.

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